

POWERSYNC: OPTIMIZING ENERGY MONITORING THROUGH ARDUINO AND RASPBERRY PI SERVER BASED CONTROL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on developing an integrated energy monitoring and control system consisting of a Windows application and private website for the TTBD0. The Windows application is designed to monitor and control electrical loads within the facility, while the private website displays statistical reports of energy consumption over specific time periods. The project incorporates an IoT system using Arduino and Raspberry Pi, along with a scale model of the TTBD0 for demonstration purposes. The primary objective is to create an integrated system that connects hardware components with software controls through LAN communication protocols, providing users real-time status updates about energy consumption via the website. The proposed solution aims to effectively monitor and control active loads on a miniature scale of the TTBD0 while tracking and displaying energy consumption data.

Keywords: Windows App, Website, Energy Monitoring and Control, Raspberry Pi, Arduino

INTRODUCTION

Electricity is an essential but expensive resource. With the continued development of technology and infrastructure, energy demand is rapidly increasing. To ensure sustainable use, it is crucial to implement systems that monitor, control, and optimize energy consumption. One of the largest energy consumers in buildings is the HVAC system (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning), which can make up 40–70% of energy usage in commercial spaces. Effective monitoring helps optimize HVAC performance, lowering energy costs and improving operational efficiency (DEE, 2013).

Globally, it's estimated that 66% of generated energy is wasted, primarily due to inefficient electrical devices, outdated insulation, and poorly optimized industrial systems. This waste significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions. Reducing this inefficiency can lead to substantial financial and environmental benefits (Ukpanah, 2024).

In the Philippines, rising electricity rates further emphasize the need for energy-saving measures. As of September 2024, Meralco increased its electricity rate by ₱0.1543 per kWh due to higher transmission costs (GMA News Online, 2024).

ISO 50001 is an international standard that provides a framework for developing energy policies, setting measurable goals, and improving energy performance through data-driven decisions. It promotes continuous improvement in energy efficiency and is applicable across industries (ISO, 2023).

A study by Akbar et al. (2023) showcased a web-based electricity monitoring system implemented in a university using a waterfall development approach. The system followed ISO 50001 principles and highlighted the benefits of real-time energy data for managing consumption and reducing costs.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

Researchers are developing software to process MQTT messages sent via Arduino ethernet shield and Raspberry Pi as a broker connection. The Arduino Uno controls electrical loads in a building, while Raspberry Pi handles web hosting and database management. The LAMP stack (Linux, Apache MySQL, PHP) is used for the software, with Node Red as the bridge between hardware and software. The frontend website uses HTML, JavaScript, and CSS, while the Windows app displays energy consumption and statistics. Data is relayed in Node Red via publish and subscribe protocol and saved on a micro-SD card for future access.

Arduino controllers and relay boards control electrical loads across buildings, scalability allows for remote management without extensive reconfiguration, and new buildings can be added to the Windows application control panel.

Figure 2
Conceptual Framework for Scalability

Statement of the Problem

This study seeks to address unmonitored energy consumption by implementing an Arduino-based monitoring and control system, accessible via software developed by researchers. To achieve this objective, the following questions were posed:

1. How can an Arduino and a Raspberry-Pi server-based monitoring and control system be effectively integrated with software?
2. Is it feasible to establish a connection between software controls, Arduino, Raspberry-Pi and the associated hardware?
3. How will the system communicate information about the status of the electrical components to the user?

Scope and Delimitations

The system uses Raspberry Pi and Arduino as core platforms and an 8-channel relay board as panelboard controllers for seamless control of electrical components. A Windows app allows university administration and guards to monitor loads and a private website for energy consumption monitoring. The prototype focuses on developing a Windows app and a private website using Raspberry Pi for monitoring and controlling electrical loads and displaying weekly consumption summary within TTBD0 building.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study will implement software prototyping methodology using the Systems Development Life Cycle (SLDC), specifically the AGILE Methodology, as the research design. AGILE was selected for its formalized yet flexible approach and emphasis on collaboration, making it particularly appropriate for the project's needs. Since this study represents a collaboration between Computer Engineering and Electronics and Communication Engineering teams, the AGILE methodology provides a logical framework that prioritizes integrity and functionality. The researchers will follow AGILE's distinct phases or stages to systematically develop and assemble the software system.

Figure 3

AGILE Development

Research Locale

The research will be conducted at Saint Mary's University in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, with specific implementation on the TTBD0 of the School of Engineering, Architecture and Information

Technology (SEAIT). The prototype is designed to monitor electrical loads and provide control through a Windows application, while also featuring a website that displays statistical graphs of power, voltage, current, and electrical consumption.

Data Gathering

For data collection, the researchers will conduct online surveys to evaluate the usability and user-friendliness of both the Windows application and website. The primary data sources will be sensor readings from the ECE group's Wattcher device, which uses Arduino to monitor energy consumption, and server logs. The Wattcher connects to a router via LAN, transmitting data to a Raspberry Pi that stores information in a MySQL database. System performance will be assessed through transmission accuracy logs and response time measurements, while the online surveys will provide qualitative feedback on usability and functionality to guide final system adjustments.

Software Description

The energy monitoring system is designed with dual capabilities: controlling electrical loads in the TTBD0 facility and visualizing power consumption data collected from sensors. Key features include graphical data displays and historical analysis capabilities that allow users to review past energy consumption patterns. The system consists of a web-based interface for monitoring and a Windows application for control, both incorporating user management at different access levels. The architecture follows a client-server model, with PHP handling server-side logic and database interactions using MySQL within a LAMP web server setup. The front-end dashboard utilizes JavaScript, HTML, and CSS, with Charts JS providing web visualization tools while Scott Plot handles visualizations for the desktop application built in C#. The system leverages Node-Red's built-in functions for scalability, while the Raspberry Pi implements encryption to secure data transmission between clients and sensors. This infrastructure is designed to be scalable, allowing for potential expansion to monitor and control multiple buildings.

System Architecture

Figure 4
System Architecture

This system architecture outlines the workflow for different user types interacting with the energy monitoring and control system. Administrators and Security Guards can actively control energy consumption at the TTBD0 (Technology Transfer and Business Development Office) through the Windows application. The SEAIT Dean and Department Heads, along with administrators, can

access the PowerSync private website to view energy consumption data. The entire system is designed exclusively for use within Saint Mary's University, specifically for the TTBDO facility. The technical infrastructure is divided between two platforms: the PowerSync Windows application operates over the Local Area Network (LAN), while the private website is hosted on a Raspberry Pi system.

PowerSync Website

Figure 5
Website Flowchart

The PowerSync Website interface is designed for use by university administration, the SEAIT dean, and department heads. System administrators (the researchers) are responsible for creating user profiles and providing login credentials to these stakeholders. To access the website, users must open a web browser, navigate to the PowerSync Website login interface, and enter their unique account name and password. After successful authentication, they are redirected to the main website interface. Both administrators and stakeholders can view the Dashboard and Statistics pages, which display energy consumption data. However, access to the user management page is restricted

exclusively to system administrators to maintain security and ensure only authorized personnel can access the website.

PowerSync Windows App

Figure 6
Windows App Flowchart

The PowerSync Windows App is accessible to both university administrators and Security Guards, with administrators using their existing accounts and Security Guards provided with separate login credentials. Once logged in, users are directed to the Dashboard, which displays key statistical data such as current active electrical loads, weekly consumption, and an hourly consumption graph. Additionally, users can access the Control Interface, which presents a visual layout of the building, highlighting rooms with active electrical loads and allowing for remote control of those components. Access is restricted to registered users, and unregistered individuals cannot bypass the login screen on either the app or the website.

Treatment of Data

The study will use qualitative methods, particularly online surveys, to assess the user-friendliness of PowerSync's interface. Due to time constraints, Python-generated test data will be used in place of actual data from Wattcher's sensors. This simulated data will be sent to a Raspberry Pi server for energy tracking and stored in a MySQL database. User feedback on both the private website and Windows application interfaces will guide the qualitative analysis, with survey results informing UI improvements. The website dashboard will present data visually through graphs, offering stakeholders insights into energy consumption trends.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter contains the results and insights gained during the development of the Windows App and website as well as the survey results. It also describes the prototype development of the Windows App and website. The prototype also consists of a miniature scale model of the TTBD0 mounted on a plywood board.

Hardware Development

Creating the miniature model of the TTBD0

1. Connect dedicated pins to the relay module to the Arduino board.
2. Connect the LED Bulbs to the relay board (Refer to figure 7).
3. Place the hardware components on a tabletop scale model (Refer to figure 8).

Figure 7

LED connection to relay board

Figure 8
Hardware components to scale model

Establishing the Raspberry Pi 4 as the server

1. Use Node-RED script to establish a connection for sensor to database connection (Refer to Figure 9).
2. Determine if the router can detect the Raspberry Pi (Refer to Figure 10).
3. Input the Linux commands through the Raspberry Pi terminal, this is where most of the applications and API's to be hosted on the Raspberry Pi are installed (Refer to Figure 11).
4. Create the database using phpMyAdmin.

Figure 9
Deployed Node- RED Flow Diagram

Figure 10
Detecting the Raspberry Pi within the router

DHCP Clients List

This page displays information of all DHCP clients on the network.

ID	Client Name	MAC Address	Assigned IP	Lease Time
1	LAPTOP-DD11BKLU	50:FE:0C:02:F7:77	192.168.0.100	00:00:43
2	raspberrypi	D8:3A:DD:E8:83:50	192.168.0.101	00:00:59

Refresh

Figure 11
Raspberry Pi Terminal

Figure 12
Login Page

A dark-themed login page for 'POWERSYNC'. The page features the title 'POWERSYNC' at the top in large white letters. Below the title are two input fields: 'Username:' and 'Password:'. At the bottom center, there is a white 'LOGIN' button. The background is a dark, textured blue.

Figure 13
Dashboard

Figure 14
Control Page

Figure 15
Login Page

Figure 16
 Dashboard for Users (University Administration, SEAIT Dean and Department Heads)

Figure 17
 Statistics Page

Figure 18
 Users Page (Only for Admins)

Analysis of the UI satisfaction survey reveals compelling results: 68% of users rated the system interface as "Excellent," while 22.67% considered it "Commendable." Only 8% of respondents assessed the UI as merely "Competent," with a minimal 1.3% finding it "Challenging."

Analysis of the user experience data reveals exceptional satisfaction levels, with 69% of respondents awarding the system interface the highest rating of "Excellent." An additional 22% classified the UI as "Commendable," while the remaining 9% evaluated it as "Competent."

Figure 19

Online Survey Results (Windows App)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Both the website and the Windows app show complete functionality based on the prototype's testing. The effectiveness of the study's goals is demonstrated by the evidence that follows.

1. The project successfully links Arduino and Raspberry-Pi communication to the hardware components through a LAN connection utilizing Node-RED and MQTT protocol.
2. The researchers successfully developed a fully operational and scalable monitoring and control system for electrical loads.
3. The system was able to establish a connection with Wattcher but due to time constraints, the researchers still opted to use generated data as data readings from Wattcher is not yet available.
4. Data from online surveys indicates remarkable user approval, with more than 90% of respondents evaluating the interface as exceeding typical standards, and notably, no participants provided negative feedback.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are for future researchers and studies aiming to enhance the current prototype. These suggestions are also directed towards the beneficiaries of this study.

1. Enhance UI design and functionality of the Windows App and Local Website.
2. Make more use of the Raspberry Pi instead of only utilizing it as a server.
3. Use ESP32 or ESP8266 rather than Arduino UNO and Wiznet 5100 since it is more cost effective and does twice the same job with just one component rather than two.

4. Improve scalability of the project by giving access to monitor and control more buildings.
5. Implement a timer indicator that displays the remaining time until electrical loads will be remotely turned off in a room.

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